

Assembled nanoparticles-based nanochannels onto a plastic flexible substrate for label-free immunosensing

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a novel, cheap, disposable and single-use assembled nanoparticles-based nanochannel platform onto a flexible substrate for label-free immunosensing is presented. This sensing platform is formed by the dip-coating of a homogeneous and assembled monolayer of carboxylated polystyrene nanospheres (PS, 200 nm and 500 nm-sized) onto the working area of flexible screen-printed ITO/PET electrodes. The spaces between the self-assembled nanospheres generate well-ordered nanochannels, with inter-PS particles distances of around 65 and 24 nm respectively. The formed nanochannels are approached for the effectively immobilization of antibodies and subsequent protein detection based on the monitoring of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ flow through diffusion and the decrease in the differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) signal upon immunocomplex formation. The obtained sensing system is nanochannel-size dependent and allows to detect human IgG (chosen as model analyte) at levels of 580 ng/mL. The system also exhibits an excellent specificity against other proteins present in real sample and shows a good performance in a human urine sample. The developed device represents an integrated and simple biodetection system which overcomes many of the limitations of previously reported nanochannels-based approaches and can be extended in the future to several other immuno and DNA detection systems.

1. Introduction

Nanochannels have been proposed in the last decade as very interesting and advantageous platforms for biosensing applications [1]. The great interest in nanoporous materials has started from the electrochemical stochastic sensing approaches which mimic the processes that occur in natural ion channels [2]. The typical experimental setup

consists of measuring the changes in electrical conductance between both sides of the membrane where a single nanochannel is inserted, inspired by the Coulter counter concept [3], which has been applied for the detection of mainly DNA [4–7] and also of proteins and other analytes [8–10].

In spite of the advantages of biological ion channels in terms of sensitivity, selectivity, and ability for the analysis of a variety of analytes, their inherent limitations related to the difficulty of keeping a natural environment in an artificial device made

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necessary the development of novel strategies for the fabrication of solid-state nanochannels based on synthetic materials [11].

Alternative technologies have been reported in the last years for the preparation of not only single but also arrays of solid-state nanochannels, which opened the way to sensing systems totally different from the stochastic based approaches. Here, anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) nanoporous membranes prepared by anodization of aluminum metal substrates [12] have been the most used materials, due to their advantageous properties and mass production opportunities. These membranes possess optical properties which have been approached in biosensing systems based on interferometric [13, 14] detection, but is in the electrochemical analysis field where their potentiality has been mostly exploited. Our group has previously reported versatile electrochemical sensing strategies using AAO nanoporous membranes, based on the monitoring of the diffusion of electroactive molecules (typically $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$) through the AAO membrane attached onto a screen-printed carbon electrotransducer (SPCE) and its differential pulse voltammetry signal change upon biomolecule recognition which allowed to detect proteins [15] and DNA [16].

Furthermore, these nanoporous membranes have been shown as excellent platforms for the analysis of real samples of, for example, human blood, due to their filtering properties, allowing minimization of matrix effects [17, 18]. However, the practical application of this sensing system is limited due to two main factors: i) the membrane and the electrotransducer have to be assembled prior the detection (not integrated system); and ii) the large thickness of Al_2O_3 membranes (60 μm approx.) made necessary the use of nanoparticle tags for the enhancement of nanochannel blockage. For these reasons, nanochannels with nanosized thickness integrated on the electrotransducer surface are highly required so as to overcome such limitations. In this context, a very interesting alternative recently proposed for the preparation of nanochannels on solid substrates would consist on the formation of highly ordered mesoporous thin film coatings, which has a great potential application in electrochemical analysis [19]. Strategies such as the use of self-assembled nanoparticle templates [20, 21], self-assembled surfactant templates [22, 23] and hard templating/nanocasting approaches [24] have been recently reported in order to get ordered nanochannel array films on electrodes. Of special relevance are the approaches based on the self-assembling of polystyrene nanospheres to build

nanostructured surfaces on transparent conductive oxide (TCO) substrates [25, 26].

Based on these principles, we report here for the first time a disposable label-free immunosensing device based on screen-printed ITO/PET (PolyEthylene Terephthalate/ Indium Tin Oxide) electrodes modified with nanochannels created by dip-coating deposition of a homogeneous monolayer of polystyrene nanospheres. The presented approach brings new opportunities in terms of robustness and mass production toward various applications for protein, DNA, and cell sensing.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals and instruments

Anti-human IgG (ref. I1886; polyclonal antibody developed in goat), anti-human IgG-FITC (ref. F3512 produced in goat), human IgG (HIgG, ref. I2511), human IgA (HIgA, ref. I4036), human IgM (HIgM, ref. I8260), goat IgG (GIgG, ref. I5256) and human serum albumin (HSA, ref. A9511) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). Working aliquots of antibodies were prepared in 0.01 M PBS buffer pH 7.4, containing 5 mM 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (APS), and [N-(3-dimethylamino) propyl-N-ethylcarbodiimide (EDC), sulfo N-hydroxysuccinimide (sulfo-NHS), while antigen aliquots were prepared in 0.01 M PBS buffer pH 7.4. Urine sample was given by a healthy male donor and used as received, without any pre-treatment. Carboxylated Polystyrene nanospheres of 500 nm and 200 nm in diameter were purchased from microParticles GmbH, Research- and Development Laboratory (Berlin). Ethanol was purchase from Sigma-Aldrich (Switzerland), Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was purchase from Fluka, Indium tin oxide coated PET (surface resistivity 60 Ω/sq) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). All chemicals were of analytical grade and their aqueous solutions were prepared in Milli-Q water.

Optical characterizations were performed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (FEI Quanta 650 FEG ESEM), and a CLSM Leica TCS-SP5 AOBs spectral fluorescence microscope (Leica Microsystems Heidelberg GmbH; Mannheim, Germany) using a Plan-Apochromatic 63 \times objective (NA 1.4, oil). All the SEM images were obtained using secondary electrons detector at high voltage (20 kV).

The electrochemical transducers used were home-made screen-printed ITO/PET electrodes (SPIEs). A semiautomatic screen-printing machine DEK248 (DEK international, Switzerland) was used

for the printing of the carbon and silver/silver chloride counter and reference electrodes respectively as well as an insulating layer. The materials and reagents used for this process were: Autostat HT5 polyester sheet (McDermid Autotype, UK), Electrodag 423SS carbon ink, Electrodag 6037SS silver/silver chloride ink, and Minico 7000 Blue insulating ink (Acheson Industries, The Netherlands). These inks were printed onto a transparent adhesive plastic Aironfix (1 mm of thickness). The electrochemical measurements were carried out using an Autolab 20 (Ecochemie, The Netherlands).

2.2. Preparation of screen-printed ITO electrodes (SPIEs)

Carbon counter and silver/silver chloride reference electrodes as well as insulating ink were screen-printed on an Ironfix layers (20 x 20 cm). After that holes of 3 mm in diameter were done on the ironfix just between the counter and reference electrodes so as to define the place of the working electrode. In addition, holes were also done in the area of connection of the electrodes so as to allow the further connection of the working electrode to the potentiostat. Finally, the electrodes were cut by each line containing 15 electrodes and adhered onto the ITO/PET surface.

2.3. Modification of SPIE with polystyrene nanospheres (PS) monolayer

The PS modification was performed on the SPIE by dip-coating technique [25]. Prior to the coating process, the SPIE was cleaned in the oxygen plasma (100 W) for 30 s, rinsed in deionized water, and dried under nitrogen flow. The PS microsphere suspension (5 w/v % aqueous suspension) was diluted with an equal volume of ethanol and dispersed on the surface of deionized water in a petri dish. By adding a few drops of 10 wt% aqueous solution of sodium dodecyl sulfate, PS microspheres form a close-packed self-assembled monolayer at the air/water interface. The electrode was gently immersed into the water with the tilt angle around 45°. The PS monolayer was transferred on the electrode surface by slowly removing the electrode from the water by maintaining the angle at 45°.

The PS-modified SPIEs were found to be stable up to 12 months when stored in a cool and dry place.

2.4. Optical and electrochemical characterizations of SPIEs modified with PS monolayer

SEM analysis for the evaluation of the homogeneity of the PS monolayers as well as for measuring the

size of the created nanochannels was performed. For this analysis, a platinum layer of 4 nm was previously sputtered on the samples so as to get a conductive layer.

SPIEs were electrochemically characterized by measuring the standard red-ox signals of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ red-ox pair using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). For this purpose the red-ox mediator, formed by 50 μL of 1 mM $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ in 0.1 M NaNO_3 were placed on the electrode surface and the voltammogram was recorded.

2.5. Antibody immobilization and immunoassay

8 μL of 1 mg/mL solution of anti-human IgG antibody in PBS buffer containing 5 mM EDC/sulfo-NHS were deposited onto the working electrode surface (where the carboxylated PS monolayer was previously created) and incubated overnight at 4 °C. Following this procedure, the antibodies were immobilized through the covalent coupling of peptide/proteins to the nanospheres. After washing in PBS buffer, 8 μL of human IgG antigen (HIgG) at different concentrations were deposited onto the working electrode surface and incubated during 2h at room temperature. PS-modified SPIEs are single-use electrodes, so all the concentrations assayed were prepared by triplicate using different SPIEs for each assay. The same experimental procedure was followed for the analysis of HIgA, HIgM, HSA, GIgG and also for the urine sample which was spiked with HIgG at 0.125, 1, 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentration levels. Antibody immobilization on the surface of the PS was evaluated by confocal microscopy. For this purpose, anti-human IgG labelled with a fluorescent tag (FITC) was incubated on the monolayer of PS following the same experimental procedure. ImageJ software (version 1.47 V) was used to determine the arbitrary units of fluorescence.

2.6. Electrochemical detection of HIgG

After washing in PBS buffer, 50 μL of 1 mM $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ in 0.1 M NaNO_3 were added. An electrochemical pre-concentration step applying a

Figure 1. (A) Schematic representation of the different materials and layers which form the SPIE, together with pictures of a sheet of transducers and of a single one; (B) Top, cyclic voltammogram (CV) performed from -400 mV to $+400$ mV in 1 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/0.1$ M $NaNO_3$. Pre-concentration step at -550 mV during 30 s, scan rate: 50 mV/s. Bottom, differential pulse voltammogram (DPV) performed from -300 mV to $+500$ mV in 1 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/0.1$ M $NaNO_3$.

potential of -0.55 V during 30 s was carried out to ensure that all the Fe^{3+} ions were transformed to Fe^{2+} . Immediately after, DPV was performed by scanning from -400 mV to $+400$ mV (step potential 10 mV, modulation amplitude 50 mV, non-stirred solution). The analytical signal corresponds to the peak of DPV current generated during the process of oxidation of $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ to $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$. The peak potential value shifts from 100 mV to 300 mV approx., depending on the degree of the blockage of the electrode. As stated before, each electrochemical measurement was performed by triplicate using different SPIEs, at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Electrochemical performance of SPIEs

Cheap, disposable, single-use screen-printed ITO electrodes (SPIEs) were prepared following the experimental procedure detailed at methods section. Figure 1A shows a schematic representation of the different materials and layers forming the final electrode, together with pictures of a sheet of transducers and a detail of a single one.

The SPIE electrodes were characterized first by cyclic voltammetry (CV), scanning from -400 mV to $+400$ mV in $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/0.1$ M $NaNO_3$. As can be observed in figure 1B (top), a well-defined pair of red-ox peaks was recorded at $+140$ mV and -48 mV, corresponding to oxidation and reduction processes of the $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ systems respectively. This behavior is similar to the one obtained for

Figure 2. SEM images of the monolayer of 200 nm (A) and 500 nm (B) PS on the working electrode of the SPIE.

well-established screen-printed electrodes such as the carbon-based ones[18]. This result demonstrates the good performance of this hybrid screen-printed ITO electrode.

Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) was also used given its higher sensitivity and better reproducibility in comparison to cyclic voltammetry measurements [15]. The DPV obtained in the range from -300 mV to $+500$ mV (Figure 1B, bottom) exhibits a well-defined current peak at approximately $+100$ mV, which also corroborates the excellent performance of SPIEs.

3.2 Evaluation of the PS modified SPIEs

As detailed in the experimental section, a previously optimized methodology which gives homogeneous PS monolayers with a low rate of defects was followed for the modification of SPIEs [25].

The morphology and homogeneity of the PS monolayer deposited onto the SPIE working electrode, prepared as detailed in the methods section, was evaluated by SEM analysis. Micrographs in figure 2 show a homogeneous monolayer of PS nanoparticles formed on the electrode for both 200 nm (A) and 500 nm (B) sized ones. Furthermore, the interparticles spaces were measured, evidencing that nanochannels of around 65 nm in diameter (500 nm in length) and of 24 nm in diameter (200 nm in length) were generated, respectively. These sizes perfectly fit the requirements of a nanochannel-based electrochemical immunosensing system, as will be detailed in the following section.

Representative samples of each batch of electrodes were characterized by SEM analysis so as to ensure the PS monolayer homogeneity and the absence of defects.

Furthermore, the efficient immobilization of

Figure 3. Confocal micrographs (xyz mode) of the 200 nm (A) and 500 nm (B) PS monolayers on SPIEs after immobilizing anti-HIgG-FITC antibodies.

antibodies on the PS surface was checked by evaluating antibodies modified with a fluorescence marker (anti-human IgG–FITC). In Figure 3, a confocal microscopy image using the xyz mode, which allows to scan the xy plane along the z axis, is shown. Fluorescence dots corresponding to the PS are clearly observed (maximum of fluorescence of around 19.2 ± 7.6 (A) and 33.2 ± 9.4 (B) arbitrary units of fluorescence for the 200 nm and 500 nm PS respectively being 0–255 the range of arbitrary units of fluorescence), demonstrating the efficient covering of the PS by antibodies.

3.3 Biosensing application: label-free detection of human IgG

SPIEs modified with PS were evaluated as biosensing platforms for the detection of proteins. The detection principle is based on the monitoring of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ diffusion through the formed nanochannels toward the electrode and its differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) signal change upon immunocomplex formation. Human IgG was chosen as model protein for the evaluation of the sensing system. Figure 4A shows a schematic representation of this sensing principle. Since the size of both antibody and antigen (human immunoglobulin G, HIgG) is $14.5 \text{ nm} \times 8.5 \text{ nm} \times 4 \text{ nm}$,^[27] the formation of the immunocomplex inside the generated nanochannels partially blocks the diffusion of the electroactive species along the nanochannel resulting in a decrease in the voltammetric signal of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ oxidation to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$. This decrease in the analytical signal is proportional to the quantity of antigen, as shown in the DPVs of figure 4B, corresponding to SPIEs modified with 500 nm PS. A logarithmic relationship between the value of the analytical signal and the HIgG concentration in the range between 1–300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Figure 4C gray line), with a correlation coefficient of 0.9812, according to the following equation: $i_p (\mu\text{A}) = -0.202 \ln [\text{HIgG}] (\mu\text{g/mL}) + 1.4347$ was obtained. The reproducibility of the method shows a RSD of 4.3 % ($n = 3$) for a HIgG concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. A limit of detection

Figure 4. (A) Schematic representation (not in scale) of the sensing principle. (B) DPV obtained in 1 mM $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]/0.1 \text{ M NaNO}_3$ for different concentrations of human IgG, from top to bottom: 1, 50, 100, 200 and 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (SPIEs modified with 500 nm PS monolayer). Pre-concentration potential: -550 mV ; pre-concentration time: 30 s; step potential: 10 mV; modulation amplitude: 50 mV; (C) Relationship between the analytical signal and the concentration of HIgG for SPIEs modified with 200 nm PS monolayer (black line) and 500 nm PS monolayer (gray line).

(LOD) of 2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of HIgG calculated as the analyte concentration giving a signal equal to the blank signal + 3SD is estimated. It was also observed that the blocking effect exerted by the immunocomplex formation was stronger when smaller was the nanochannel diameter, as expected. As summarized in Figure 4C (black line), in the case of the 200 nm sized PS, the range of logarithmic response was found between 0.125–200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9975, according to the following equation: $i_p (\mu\text{A}) = -0.109 \ln [\text{HIgG}] (\mu\text{g/mL}) + 2.1501$. In this case the reproducibility of the method showed a RSD of 3.9 % ($n = 3$) for a HIgG concentration of 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The higher sensitivity of the biosensing system prepared with the 200 nm sized PS is evidenced. A limit of detection of 580 ng/mL of HIgG was estimated. The better performance of the immunosensor prepared with the 200 nm sized PS, in terms of sensitivity, detection range and linear response make this system optimum for further biosensing applications.

It is assumed that, in spite of the well-controlled preparation methodology and characterization, defects can be present in some SPIEs affecting the reproducibility of the biosensing system. However, the reproducibility of the results is excellent (RSD around 4%), evidencing that these possible defects

Figure 5. Relative decrease of the analytical signal obtained for immunoassays performed for 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of specific protein (HIgG) and of proteins that could interfere in real sample analysis: HIgA, HIgM and HSA. The results obtained for a goat IgG (GIgG) and for a urine sample are also shown. SPIEs modified with 200 nm PS monolayer are used.

in the PS monolayer are not relevant from the biosensing point of view.

The performance of the system is much better than the previously obtained in label-free approaches using commercial anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) membranes (detection limits of 100-200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ depending on the pore size assayed) and screen-printed carbon electrodes. [15] These results are in agreement with the expected, since the shorter channel lengths created with the nanospheres (200-500 nm) compared with those of the commercial membranes (60 μm) allow a better blocking with lower quantities of antigen. In addition to the better sensitivity, this novel approach presents a simpler and more integrated sensing system. After the PS monolayer creation and antibody immobilization, SPIEs can be offered as really disposable biosensing devices for a one-step sensing procedure, enormously reducing the time of analysis. The developed sensor is aimed for one use only. It should be a disposable device that would operate in the same way as a glucose biosensor does.

3.4 Specificity of the immunosensing system

The specificity of the immunosensing system against the main proteins present in physiological fluids and that could interfere in the detection of HIgG was evaluated using the SPIEs modified with 200 nm PS monolayer. Human serum albumin (HSA), human IgA (HIgA) and human IgM (HIgM) were selected since they are the more predominant proteins in i.e. human serum, together with HIgG [28]. Furthermore, the specificity against other IgG

Spiked HIgG ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Current in PBS (μA)	Current in urine (μA)	Recovery (%)
0.125	2.38	2.29	96.2
1	2.15	2.03	94.4
10	1.90	1.79	94.2
100	1.65	1.58	95.8

Table 1. Spike and recovery assay data. The study was done by spiking 0.125, 1, 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of HIgG in a urine sample ($n=3$ for each sample) and the recovery % was obtained as comparing with PBS buffer.

(from goat: GIgG) was also evaluated. The results are shown in figure 5, where the relative decrease of the analytical signal ($(i_{\text{max}}-i)/i_{\text{min}} \times 100$) is represented for the different proteins evaluated. As observed in the figure, for a fixed protein concentration as high as 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, the specific protein gives a relative decrease in the signal of more than a 90%, while for the rest of the proteins this decrease is of only around 5-7%. This small unspecific signal, probably due to a combination of unspecific absorptions and cross-reactivity of the antibodies can be considered as non-relevant for practical applications, considering that the concentration of HIgG i.e. in human serum is 5-10 times higher than that of HIgA and HIgM [28].

3.5. Performance in real samples: spike and recovery

The performance of the immunosensing system in a real complex matrix such as human urine was also evaluated. This kind of sample was selected since the presence of very low levels of HIgG in urine is indicative of diseases such as Amyloidosis, Leukemia, Myeloma, nephropathy or Waldenstrom's macroglobulinemia [29]. A urine sample from a healthy donor, without any pre-treatment, was analysed. As shown in figure 5, it gave a decrease of the analytical signal of only around a 6%. These results suggest that very low unspecific absorptions of the components of urine take place on the interparticle spaces. Most of these components are probably removed during the washing step in PBS buffer performed after the immunoreaction (see section 2.6), evidencing the filtering properties of the as-prepared nanochannels.

Finally, spike and recovery experiment was performed to determine whether HIgG detection is affected by the biological sample matrix of urine. The human urine sample of a healthy donor with spiked HIgG at levels between 0.125 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ were evaluated. The obtained analytical signals and

their comparison with those obtained in PBS buffer are included in table 1. As shown in the table, recoveries of around 95% for all the concentrations assayed were obtained. These results demonstrate that this technology has high recovery rates from human urine samples making it a promising alternative for the determination of HIgG in a real scenario.

4. Conclusions

A novel nanochannels-based biosensing platform on cheap, disposable and single-use screen-printed ITO electrodes (SPIEs) has been developed. Homogeneous monolayers of assembled polystyrene nanospheres (PS) have been successfully deposited on the working surface of the SPIEs by dip coating, creating well-ordered nanochannels in the inter-particle spaces. Antibodies are efficiently immobilized on the carboxy-modified PS through covalent binding, allowing the capturing of specific antigens and further quantification by voltammetric evaluation of the nanochannels blockage due to the immunocomplex formation. The limit of detection obtained with such a label-free approach is lower when smaller is the PS diameter, and consequently the nanochannels size, reaching values as low as 580 ng/mL for human IgG, chosen as model protein. The system is highly specific against the main proteins present in physiological fluids and that could interfere in the detection of HIgG. Furthermore, low matrix effects are found when analysing a human urine sample, demonstrating the ability of the sensing system to perform analysis in real scenarios.

This novel system overcomes many of the limitations of previously reported approaches based on commercial anodic aluminium oxide (AAO) membranes in terms of integration and sensitivity, representing a really disposable biosensing device for a one-step sensing procedure. Moreover, this approach brings new opportunities in terms of robustness and mass production toward various applications for protein, DNA, and cell sensing.

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